

Instruct-ULTRA

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Integrating Structural Biology

Instruct-ULTRA

WP4 - Advancing Instruct through Instruct- Ultra

Lead Beneficiary: P1-Instruct

Leader: Ray Owens (P2-UOXF)

Deliverable D 4.1 Call 1 launched for developing new service provision of existing technologies and selection of qualifying projects.

Contractual delivery date: 30th September 2017

Actual delivery date: 13th October 2017

Author of this deliverable: Ray Owens

Contributing partner: P1-Instruct, P12-CIRMMMP

Project objective

To introduce new and innovative technology into the portfolio of services provided by Instruct facilities to take account of advances newly available in structural biology research.

Executive summary

Work package 4 comprises two calls for proposals from the beneficiary partners to contribute to either Task 4.1 introducing new services or Task 4.2. providing access to new communities. Each partner has been allocated personnel resources and joint proposals from partners have been encouraged in order to effectively resource projects. Partners were asked for expressions of interest for Call 1 projects in May 2017 and the terms of reference of the project call discussed and agreed at the Instruct-ULTRA General Assembly on 24th May, held in Brno. Joint proposal discussions were initiated in Q2 2017 and collaborative negotiations followed during

the drafting stages. Formal applications to Call 1 were opened via the Instruct website and the closing date for submissions was the 29th September 2017. Review of proposals by three members of the Instruct-ULTRA Scientific Advisory Board will be handled via email and, on the basis of feedback, projects will be selected by the Executive Board during Q4 2017. Projects are expected to start in January 2018 and run for up to two years.

D 4.1 report

Introduction

Structural biology methods are continuously developing with new instrumentation and work flows. To ensure that Instruct-ERIC continues to offer access to state-of-the art technology, Work Package 4 of Instruct-ULTRA will facilitate the introduction of new techniques into the services provided by Instruct-ERIC. Further, this work package will aim to support new specialist services in member countries that do not currently host Instruct Centres, namely Belgium, Denmark, Portugal and Slovakia, and hence foster the development of new centres and expand the Instruct user community, including the industry sector.

Description of Work

Call 1 asks for pilot projects to exploit technologies that are either being developed or have been implemented by beneficiary partners, but are not currently available as an access service. All beneficiary institutions participating in Instruct-ULTRA including those not currently operating as Instruct Centres can propose new infrastructure services. Call 1 projects will be selected that will introduce new and innovative technology and hence expand the services offered by Instruct. The strategic value of proposals that will promote the establishment of new Instruct Centres in the beneficiary partners will be taken into consideration. For successful projects the beneficiary partners will be expected to (1) to test the new service(s) as both users and providers (2) evaluate and modify the infrastructure service as necessary (3) develop an appropriate procedure with unit costs for delivering the service (4) report on the outcome of the project. Call 1 proposals will be reviewed in Year 1 and testing will commence in Year 2.

Identification and selection of projects

The project call was opened on publicising through the Instruct website with a link (<https://www.structuralbiology.eu/submit-proposal?t=instruct>) to the submission form specifically designed for Call 1 (see Appendix for screen shots of application guidelines and submission form)

Applications will be sent to an external review panel comprising three to five experts who will be asked to comment on proposals and if necessary provide a prioritization. The panel will be drawn from the Instruct-ULTRA Science Advisory Board (Table 1).

Name	Affiliation
Stephen Burley	Rutgers University, New Jersey, USA
Wah Chui	Baylor College of Medicine, Texas, USA
Stephen Cusack	EMBL, Grenoble, France
Maria Flocco	Astrazeneca, Cambridge, UK
Arwen Pearson	University of Hamburg, Germany

Table 1 Instruct-ULTRA Scientific Advisory Board appointed by the General Assembly meeting (23rd May 2017).

The reviewers will receive proposals electronically and without disclosing the name of the applicant and will be asked to comment on the following aspects of the proposed new service technology:-

- (1) Added value of the new technology service in terms of novelty, potential for innovation and complementarity with existing Instruct services.
- (2) Technical feasibility in terms of development of the new technology into a reliable and robust service that can be delivered to external users.
- (3) Scientific impact in terms of experimental output and expansion of user base for instruct including industry, enabled by the new service technology.
- (4) Strategic value in terms of establishing new Instruct Centres in member states of Instruct-ERIC (UK, France, Italy, Slovakia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Portugal, Israel, Netherlands).

Reviewers will be asked to provide an overall score according to the following definitions 1-5 (table 2).

Table 2 Scoring sheet for Project

Score	Definition	Guidance
5	Excellent New service/technology that is highly innovative and, meets the majority of the assessment criteria to a very high level.	Implementable
4	Very Good New service/technology that is innovative and meets the majority of the assessment criteria to a high level.	Implementable
3	Good New service/technology that has merit and meets the majority of the assessment criteria to an adequate level.	Potentially Implementable
2	Satisfactory New service/technology that is potentially of some merit, and meets some of the assessment criteria to an adequate level, but which is not significantly innovative.	Not Implementable in present form
1	Not Competitive New service/technology that does not meet the majority of the assessment criteria to an adequate level and is not innovative.	Not Implementable

On the basis of feedback from reviewers, projects will be selected by the Instruct Executive Board and proposers notified by end of December 2017. Pilot proposals will be managed using the Instruct proposal/administration portal at www.structuralbiology.eu.

Table 3 List of project proposals submitted for WP4 Call1

APPID	Title	Lead Instruct-ULTRA partner
329	Structure-based/ligand-based drug design platform, including ligand fishing by equilibrium dialysis coupled with high resolution mass spectrometry	P7-NHRF
332	Analysis of large nucleic acids by mass spectrometry	P10-CNRS

335	Towards standard APIs for the exchange of metadata between homelab LIMS software and ISPyB	P9-OULU UNIVERSITY
338	Xtal Controller: Monitoring and optimizing the production of micro- and nanometer-sized crystals for MX and SFX	P10-CNRS
341	Advanced ITC microcalorimetry platform for biological applications	P10-CNRS
350	Glycobiology	P16-CEM USTAV SAV
353	Cryo-EM under anaerobic conditions	P10-CNRS
359	Towards the development of two-colour localization microscopy based on primed-photoconversion at the Institute for Structural Biology	P10-CNRS
362	Integrated magnetic resonance approaches to characterize highly mobile proteins and weak protein-protein (ligand) complexes	P12-CIRMMP
365	Development of a Predictor for NMR and Protein Structure Determination - Towards Establishing a Danish INSTRUCT Center	P6-AU
368	Focused ion beam micromachining of cellular lamellas for in situ structural biology	P4- MU

Appendix Screen shots of Instruct-ULTRA Work package 4 call 1 screen shots of application guidelines and submission form on the Instruct website

Instruct-ULTRA Work Package 4 Call 1

Call 1 asks for pilot projects to exploit technologies that are either being developed or have been implemented by beneficiary partners, but are not currently available as an access service. All beneficiary institutions participating in Instruct-ULTRA including those not currently operating as Instruct Centres can propose new infrastructure services. Call 1 projects will be selected that will introduce new and innovative technology and hence expand the services offered by Instruct. The strategic value of proposals that will promote the establishment of new Instruct Centres in the beneficiary partners will be taken into consideration. For successful projects the beneficiary partners will be expected to (1) to test the new service(s) as both users and providers (2) evaluate and modify the infrastructure service as necessary (3) develop an appropriate business model for delivering the service (4) report on the outcome of the project.

Applications to Call 1 will be sent to an external review panel comprising three to five members of The Instruct-ULTRA SAB who will be asked to comment on proposals and provide a prioritisation. Two members Instruct-ULTRA with no voting rights will help the panel decide if proposals address the Instruct goals, and will complement the panel. Final selection will be made by the Instruct-ULTRA Executive Board.

Call Submission Guidelines

Case for support (500 words max):

Please address the following points:

1. Briefly describe the method/technique that will be developed as a new service technology for Instruct-ERIC.
2. Briefly describe how the method/technique will complement the existing portfolio of services.
3. Outline a plan for testing the method/technique in service mode with reference to specific use cases.

Budget

Summarise with a justification the resources required (staff and consumables) to carry out the project.

Collaborators

List any other Instruct-ULTRA partners or external collaborators who will make an in kind contribution to the project.

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(a) Project call on the public Instruct web page

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Instruct-ULTRA Work Package 4 Call 1

Application Details [Help?](#)

Application Title:

Case for Support:

Budget:

Collaborators:

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(b) submission page for registered Instruct users that are participants in Instruct-ULTRA